

ORTHOPEDEST-DENTIST-DEONTOLOGIST IN DENTAL PROSTHETIC SURGERY FACTOR COLLATION

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ABSTRACT

This article based on the study of the grazed concepts of Bioethics and proves the relationship of Bioethics in dental practice. In addition indicating the position of deontology in orthopedic dentistry. Orthopedist difficulties in the adaptation period of patients to dentures imposed by dentist mentioned. Based on this, the deontological relationship between the orthopedic dentist and the patient explained.

Relevance: The bioethical attitude towards the human body is the practice of medicine including is the peculiarity of Dentistry. Patient's mouth as a dental bioethical object emptiness is a unique organ system of the human body. In bioethics in the study of this object, there are three it is necessary to adhere to the most important principle.

1. do not hurt, do good;
- 2.dental approach the object responsibly;
3. remember that health is above all raw.

The oral cavity is a unique part of the human body and performs many functions. It was preceded by in relation to the doctor it is mandatory to be in bioethical responsibility by the dentist. The health of the whole organism is the full-fledged limb of a person (as a person) society the ability to divide is significantly dependent on the health of the oral cavity. Every doctor the dentist must take care of the patient's oral cavity tissue, one of the tissues it is obliged to take the necessary preventive measures to ensure integrity. Dentist treatment when choosing a style, it is as important as ensuring technological, medical and maximum comfort must comply with the principles. The dentist is not only a professional social worker, but also is considered a moral person. Moral relationship between doctor and patient medical is a necessary aspect of activity. Moral relationship between dentist and patient connection through mutual respect and trust based on the principles of professional medical ethics (Vartanyan G.A., Gukasyan D. S., Borisov B. P., 2010). Bioethics when the content of medical deontology is focused on the wishes of the

doctor the content of its principles is aimed at protecting the patient. Bioethics new biomedicine as a doctrine on the social, legal, moral consequences of its technology is defined. United States and British Association of physicians in 2002 The British magazine Lancet proposed to adopt a new code of medical ethics published the article. Health system for doctors and patients social justice a system was created taking into account the principles. According to this, the medical care of it was advanced that the quantity and quality should not depend solely on the patient's solvency. Patients have a much higher need for orthopedic dentistry. Specialist dentist, works in collaboration with other orthopedic colleagues and faces various ethical challenges can come. In the practice of an orthopedic dentist, bioethical indicators are diverse.

They are includes the following:

- doctor and patient attitude;
- interaction in the professional group of orthopedic dentists;
- relationship of orthopedic stomatolg with other medical specialist groups;
- ownership and benefit relations in orthopedic dental practice;
- attitude to new scientific achievements and their use in orthopedic practice criteria;
- medicines used in orthopedic dental practice are in price grade relationships;
- aesthetic standards of orthopedic dental care;
- moral condition of the patient in relation to health and doctor's recommendations;

Another approach to determining bioethical standards in dentistry is Loyola University (Illinois, USA) scientist David T. It was adopted by Ozar, who said that " - of Dentistry the bioethical basis is the system of values recognized in the developed profession". They are is regulated as follows:

1. Equality between life and health;
2. Correct and painless operation of stomatolg into the oral cavity;
3. Patient autonomy;
4. Professional practice;
5. Achieving aesthetic and cosmetic gòzality of patients;
6. Convenient price-navo;
7. Other external factors (David.T.O, 1988).

Purpose: In orthopedic dentistry, taking into account moral and diontological principles it is easy and convenient for the patient to improve the quality of professional activity and put prostheses ensure compatibility.

Materials and methods: Analysis of scientific literature and statistics, informationa search was carried out. We are also talking about the introduction of Bioethics in Central Asia and the West countries have studied the data.

Result: The period of adaptation of patients to the inserted prosthesis includes 3 stages:

1. Before the practice of an orthopedic dentist and eliminate defects of severe tooth tolerance the period of departure to the settlement. Attendance of patients to the clinic and implementation of the treatment plan includes (2 weeks and more).
2. The stage of obtaining a mold from the patient and preparing a prosthesis (from 1 to 2 weeks).

3. The stage of adjusting the prosthesis to the patient and restoring the defect. This stage is the longest it can take from 6 months to 1 year, being of the stages that it takes. So in patients with strong knowledge and practice from the dentist orthopedist so that the tooth row defect can be restored together, deontological hardship and patience are required. Therefore, both the doctor and the patient the psychological and deontological relationship of mutual trust and respect between them is strong must be. Only then will each inserted prosthesis be able to perform its function to the maximum. This is to be satisfied by a specialist doctor and the treated patient in dentistry defines the basis of bioethics. In place of the conclusion, it can be said that based on this study, deontology is orthopedic we studied the relationship with dentistry. Because the dental row defect is currently the number of patients observed is increasing, which increases the demand for an orthopedic dentist. So the orthopedist, along with having a good qualification and experience, the patient must take into account the characteristics of the individual. Elimination of defects in patients it is necessary to selectively put a prosthesis on the structure and achieve aesthetic, cosmetic beauty through it. Patient politeness of the stages of adaptation to the prosthesis laid by a specialist dentist must explain correctly with, that is, take a psychemotional approach to the issue. Of these all reflect dental deontology.

References:

- 1.Ахмадов И. Н. КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ И ПРИНЦИПЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ АЛЛЕРГИЧЕСКОГО СТОМАТИТА ПРИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИИ ЧАСТИЧНЫХ И ПОЛНЫХ СЪЕМНЫХ ПЛАСТИНОЧНЫХ ПРОТЕЗОВ //ББК 72 И66. – 2021. – С. 262.
- 2.Shavkatovich O. R., Nizomitdin A. I. EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF OSTEOPLASTIC MATERIAL" STIMUL-OSS" IN SAMARKAND //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 612-617.
- 3.Nizomitdin A. I. THERAPEUTIC EFFECT OF IMPROVED ENAMEL SURFACE PREPARATION TECHNIQUE IN THE TREATMENT OF ACUTE INITIAL CARIES OF TEMPORARY TEETH IN CHILDREN //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 440-445.
- 4.Ахмадов И. ОБЗОР СРЕДСТВ ДЛЯ ФИКСАЦИИ ЗУБНЫХ ПРОТЕЗОВ //ЗБІРНИК НАУКОВИХ ПРАЦЬ НАУКОВО-ПРАКТИЧНА КОНФЕРЕНЦІЯ З МІЖНАРОДНОЮ УЧАСТЮ ТА НАВЧАЛЬНИМ ТРЕНІНГОМ З ОВОЛОДІННЯМ ПРАКТИЧНИМИ НАВИКАМИ «СУЧАСНІ МЕТОДИ ДІАГНОСТИКИ, ПРОФІЛАКТИКИ ТА ЛІКУВАННЯ ОСНОВНИХ СТОМАТОЛОГІЧНИХ ЗАХВОРЮВАНЬ». – 2021. – С. 43.
- 5.Nizomitdin A. I. Modern Methods of Odontopreparation for MetalCeramic for Beginner Prosthodontists //Eurasian Medical Research Periodical. – 2023. – Т. 18. – С. 98-102.
- 6.Ахмадов И. Н. Нарушения в системе перекисного окисления липидов при парадантозе //IQRO. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 124-127.
- 7.Sanaqulov J., Sadriyev N., Axmadov I. KERAMİK KIRITMANING BOSHQA RESTAVRATSIYA VOSITALARI BILAN SOLISHTIRISH //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9 Part 2. – С. 22-26.
- 8.Sadriev N., Sanakulov J., Akhmedov I. ANALYSIS OF PROFILE TELERENTGOGRAM AND PLANNING ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT OF DENTAL ANOMALIES AND DEFORMATIONS IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS USING AUTOMATED EQUIPMENT WITH ELEMENTS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE" ALLEGRO" //Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций.

– 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 69-71.

9.Ахмадов И. КЕРАМИЧЕСКОЙ ИНКРУСТАЦИИ ПО СРАВНЕНИЮ С ДРУГИМИ ВОССТАНОВИТЕЛЬНЫМИ ПРОЦЕДУРАМИ //Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 9. – С. 126-131.

10.Ахмадов И. VARK КАФЕДРЫ ОРТОПЕДИЧЕСКОЙ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ //Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 9. – С. 132-136.

11.Akhmadov I. et al. VARK DEPARTMENT OF ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10 Part 3. – С. 57-61.

12.Akhmadov I. et al. CERAMIC INLAYS COMPARED TO OTHER RESTORATION PROCEDURES //Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 186-191.

13.Sadriev N. et al. DENTAL IMPLANTOLOGY IN THE DIABETIC PATIENTS //Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 44-48.

14.Sadriev N. et al. DENTAL IN CHILDREN WITH TRAUMATIC STOMATITIS COMPLEX DENTAL TREATMENT OF DISEASES AND THEIR EVALUATION OF PREVENTION //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10 Part 3. – С. 62-65.

15.Sadriev N. et al. PREVENTION OF PROSTHETIC DENTISTRY //Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 54-57.

16.Санакулов Ж., Садриев Н., Ахмадов И. КОМПЛЕКСНОЕ ОРТОПЕДО-ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ АНОМАЛИЙ И ДЕФОРМАЦИЙ ЗУБОЧЕЛЮСТНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ В СФОРМИРОВАННОМ ПРИКУСЕ С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ ЛАЗЕРНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ АННОТАЦИЯ //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9 Part 2. – С. 27-31.

17.Jamshed S. PREVALENCE OF PHYSIOLOGICAL BITE FORMS IN PEOPLE WITH DIFFERENT FACE TYPES //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 451-454.

18.Nazhmiddinovich S. N., Obloberdievich S. J. Optimization of Orthopedic Treatment of Dentition Defects in Patients with Chronic Diseases of the Gastrointestinal Tract //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2023. – Т. 17. – С. 157-159.

19.Obloberdievich S. J. Grade States Fabrics Periodontal by Clinical Indexes //Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 175-180.

20.Sanakulov Zhamshed Obloberdi ugli, Zubaydullaeva Maftuna Alisher kizi, & Norbutaev Alisher Berdikulovich. (2022). CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL RESULTS OF ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH PARTIAL ABSENCE OF TOOTH. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(1), 958–960. Retrieved from <https://www.giirj.com/index.php/giirj/article/view/1171>

21.Nazhmiddinovich S. N. OPTIMIZATION OF ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF DENTAL DEFECTS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GASTROINTESTINAL DISEASES //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 10. – С. 53-58.

22.Najmiddinovich S. N. et al. CARIES IN SCHOOL CHILDREN AND TREATMENT PREVENTIVE MEASURES //American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research. –

2023. – Т. 16. – С. 44-49.

23.Najmiddinovich S. N. et al. PREVENTION PROGRAM DENTAL DISEASES IN SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN //Intent Research Scientific Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 24-31.

24.Sadriev N. et al. TISHLARNI PROTEZLASH JARAYONIDA ORTOPED STOMATOLOGNING DEONTOLOGIK MUNOSABATGA KIRISHISHI //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11 Part 3. – С. 109-113.

25.Sadriev N. et al. PANDEMIYA SHAROITIDA STOMATOLOGIK FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLAR BO'YICHA KO'RSATMALAR //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11 Part 3. – С. 95-99.

26.Khayrullayevna O. N., Ulugbek K. AESTHETIC RESTORATION USING ZIRCONIUM CROWNS //Intent Research Scientific Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 83-90.

27.Anvarovich E. S., Qobilovna B. Z. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS METHODS OF GUM RETRACTION IN ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2023. – Т. 11. – С. 79-83.

